

TO IDENTIFY THE SOURCES IN PRODUCTION OF COTTON IN MARATHWADA REGION.

Shelar P.R., Dr. S. S. More and Ravi.K. Hatagale.

1. M.Sc. Scholar 2. Head and Coordinator Cost of cultivation Scheme, VNMKV, Parbhani

3. Jr. Research Assistant, Department of Agril Economics, VNMKV, Parbhani, Maharashtra, India.

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Abstract

Cotton (*Gossypium spp*) the white gold is one of the most important cash crop in the world. although cotton is primary a fibre crop, it is also used as a food and feed crop. Cotton seed being the world's second most oilseeds used for culinary purposes and the oil cake residue is a protein rich feed for ruminant livestock. Cotton play an important role in Indian economy as it contribute significantly to both agriculture and industry in terms of farm income employment and export earnings. On the acreage front, India is a world leader in term of area under cotton, account for about 24 per cent of the Total world area under cotton cultivation and 5 per cent of Total cultivated area in India. In terms of production, India ranks fourth in the world trailing behind China, Uzbekistan and USA. Maharashtra is the largest cotton growing state in the country. It covers about 38.06 lakh hectare area and is 1st in India followed by Gujarat. The total production and total productivity is 89 lakh bales and 396 kg/ha in 2016-17, respectively.

Keywords - Cotton (*Gossypium spp*), oil cake, agriculture and industry, Production and Productivity.

Introduction

Cotton (*Gossypium spp.*), the 'white gold' is one of the most important cash crop in the world. Cotton is primarily a fiber crop, it is also used as a food and feed crop. Cotton seed being the world's second most oilseeds used for culinary purposes and the oil cake residue is a protein rich feed for ruminant livestock.

The average productivity of cotton in the State is 189 kg lint per ha as against, 556 kg in Punjab, 454 kg in Haryana, 417 kg in Gujrat and 384 kg in Andhra Pradesh. The main reason for low productivity of cotton on Maharashtra is its large scale rain-fed cultivation (97 per cent).

Study is helpful to extension and economic researchers to study the overall profile of cotton cultivars in the selected study area. In this area, production and sources in production etc and other various factors are covered.

The study is also helpful to research workers to conduct further detailed study of this topic on large area with more precision and better planning to have good research findings and limitation the results of study are based on data collected for only one agriculture year. Data collected from various government publication. Data related to Marathwada district only.

Decomposition of Production Growth

Shetty (1970), did decomposition analysis to measure the contributions of area, yield and changes in crop pattern to the growth of agricultural production for the period 1920-21 to 1954-55. It was further revealed that acreage expansion was the most important source of growth of production at the all India level, the contributions of area and crop pattern accounting for nearly 90 per cent of the increase in agricultural production. Thus the increase in agricultural production during the period covered seems to have been realized mainly through the expansion of area rather than through improvement in the productivity of land.

Sharma (1977), decomposed the total change in the value of production into seven components using the decomposition procedure depicted as under

$$X = P_0A_0AY \times A_0Y_0AP + P_0Y_0AA + P_0AAAY + A_0AYAP + YAAAP + AAAYAP$$

Where, X was output in value term, A = Area under the crop, Y = Yield, P = Price of the crop and subscript 0 represent base periods and A represent the change. The first three terms on the right hand side indicates the yield, area and price effects. Where by the remaining represents their interaction.

Venkataramanam and Prahaldchar (1980), followed decomposition scheme suggested by Minnas and Vaidyanathan to Analyze the relative contribution of component element, viz., area, growth, yield growth, cropping pattern changes and the interaction between yield growth and cropping pattern changes to the growth in crop output in the six states under study during the period 1950-55 to 1970-75. In Maharashtra, the contribution from yield growth was negligible crop pattern changes and area growth were the major contributing factor to the output growth.

Teja *et al.* (2017) studied the performance of total oilseeds in India, using times series data, collected from 1949-50 to 2014-15. The total period from 1949-50 to 2014-15 was divided into four sub-periods i.e. period I, II, III and IV. The contribution of area and productivity to the total production of total oilseeds were analyzed using decomposition analysis. It was evident from the result that, the production of oilseeds was influenced by the yield effect, which was 58.69, 50.41 and 44.74 per cent in period IV, period II and period III, respectively. Contrary to that, in period I, production of oilseeds was influenced by the area effect, with 95.24 per cent. In the period I, production was chiefly contributed by area effect. However, a meager contribution of 3.37 per cent is only contributed by yield effect. This inferred that the production of total oilseeds was stunted due to the restriction of total oil oilseeds cultivation to marginal lands coupled with poor management practices and incidence of pests and diseases. Lower contribution of yield effect concluded that the technology has not made any positive impact on the total oilseeds production during this period. In period II, total oilseeds production was contributed majorly (50.41 %) by yield effect

Decomposition Analysis: -

To measure the relative contribution of area and yield towards the total output, a decomposition model suggested by Minhas & Vidhyanathan and redeveloped by Sharma will be used. In the decomposition analysis, the change in production is taken as the effect of three factors such as yield effect, area effect and interaction effect.

Minhas and Vaidyanathan (1965) mentioned the importance of technology in the growth of agriculture they did not bring in their analysis. It should be noted that irrigation is very important factor whose effects spans all the component of crop output which is not studied by any of the studies. One needs to consider this entire factor and develop a decomposition scheme. It would be good area to explore the source of agricultural growth through decomposition analysis in the recent past as agricultural growth is decelerating and by doing so an effective policy measure could be implemented for a better growth performance in agriculture.

Sharma (1977) also decomposed the total change in the value of production into seven components using the decomposing procedure depicted as under

$$X = P_0A_0\Delta Y \times A_0Y_0\Delta P + P_0Y_0\Delta A + P_0\Delta A \Delta Y + P_0\Delta A \Delta Y + Y\Delta A \Delta P + \Delta A \Delta Y \Delta P$$

Where, X was output in the value term, A = Area under the crops, Y = Yield, r = Price of the crops and subscript 0 represent base period and Δ represent the change. The first three terms on the right hand side indicates the yield, area and price effects. Where by the remaining represents their interaction

$$\Delta P = A_0 \Delta Y + Y_0 \Delta A + \Delta A \Delta Y$$

Where,

ΔP = Change in production

A_0 = Area in base year

Y_0 = Yield in the base year

Y_1 = Yield in the current year

A_t = Area in the current year

ΔA = Change in area ($A_t - A_0$)

ΔY = Change in the yield ($Y_1 - Y_0$)

Change in production = Yield effect + Area effect +

Interaction effect.

Thus, the total change in production was decomposed into yield, area and interaction effect

t, while 36.75 per cent of contribution was made by area effect.

Result and Discussion

A quantitative assessment of contribution of the various factors to production in the districts of Marathwada region is helpful in reorienting the programmes and setting priorities of agricultural development to achieve higher growth rates of agricultural production. There are many factor which affect the growth of crops output. The factors believed to affect the production of crops viz. area, yield and their interaction have been considered in the present study. The result of decomposition scheme was worked for two equally divided sub periods and overall periods for cotton crops as pooled of 28 years and decomposition scheme was worked for three equally divided sub periods and overall periods for cotton crops as pooled of 28 years.

Growth decomposition of cotton in districts of Marathwada region and at Maharashtra state

The decomposition of cotton production in area, yield and interaction effects is presented in table 4.10 and which demonstrate the, per cent contribution of area, yield and their interaction for increasing production of cotton in all districts of Marathwada region. During period-I, Interaction effect was Negative for all the districts except Jalna Beed and Parbhani district recorded positive interaction effect i.e.0.05 9.08 and 11.37 per cent. The Latur district was recorded highest area effect i.e 52.60 per cent. Lowest area effect was found in the Nanded district i.e. 2.91 per cent.

During period-II, it was noticed that yield effect has got domination over the area effect. The Osmanabad district was recorded highest area effect i.e 47.69 per cent. Lowest area effect was found in the Parbhani district i.e. 1.78 per cent. Highest yield effect was found in the Parbhani district i.e. 106.31 per cent. During this period also, yield effect was more than area effect on production of cotton crops in all districts of Marathwada region.

During overall period, The Osmanabad district was recorded highest area effect i.e 48.88 per cent. Interaction effect was negative for all the districts except Aurangabad Jalna Beed Latur Osmanabad Nanded district i.e. 19.01, 21.12, 4.64, 9.13, 31.07 and 7.91 per cent respectively.

Agarwal *et al.* (2014) it was revealed that, the area under cotton production in Madhya Pradesh plays a major role in growth of cotton production due to area effect the productivity effect was influencing cotton production. whereas interaction effect was very low to enhance cotton production in the state.

Table 1.1: decomposition of cotton in districts of Marathwada region and at Maharashtra state

Sr.	Name	Period-I			Period-II			Overall Period		
		Area effect	Yield effect	Interaction effect	Area effect	Yield effect	Interaction effect	Area effect	Yield effect	Interaction effect
01	Aurangabad	22.24	103.51	-25.75	2.35	88.59	9.05	9.02	71.97	19.01
02	Jalna	17.07	82.89	0.05	4.40	71.28	24.31	6.47	72.40	21.12
03	Beed	44.01	46.91	9.08	5.23	88.69	6.08	38.35	57.01	4.64
04	Latur	52.60	76.93	-29.53	29.40	47.48	23.12	32.62	58.25	9.13
05	Osmanabad	NIL	NIL	NIL	47.69	33.77	18.54	48.88	20.05	31.07
06	Nanded	2.91	110.83	-13.74	2.78	88.73	8.49	7.98	84.11	7.91
07	Parbhani	14.86	73.77	11.37	1.78	106.31	-8.08	14.26	95.04	-9.30
08	Hingoli	NIL	NIL	NIL	9.54	94.79	-4.33	15.74	113.48	-29.22
09	Marathwada region	8.67	104.39	-13.06	9.15	89.77	1.08	9.15	89.77	1.08
10	Maharashtra State	5.47	97.32	-2.79	8.60	91.67	-0.27	8.60	91.67	-0.27

Period-I: 1988-89 to 2001-02, Period-II: 2002-03 to 2015-16, Overall Period: 1988-89 to 2015-16.

References

1. Agarwal, P.K., Divya, P., Yadav, P., Sing, O.P., (2014), "Trends of area, production and productivity of soybean crops in Madhya Pradesh". *National Academy of Agricultural Science*, **32**:(3-4): 797-800.
2. Alamian, M., Eshraghi, F., Joolaie, R. (2013), "Decomposition of growth of agricultural products value in Golestan province", *International Journal of Agriculture and Crop Sciences*, **6** (3): 139-143.
3. Basu, A.K., Narayanan, S.S. and Singh, P. (1992), "Cotton production and improvement in India". *Agricultural Situation in India*, **47** (5) : 365-373.
4. Borthakur, N. and Krishnamoorthy, S. (1997), "Sources of growth and Instability in the production of Rape and Mustard in Assam". *Agricultural Situation in India* , **54** (1): 17-19.
5. Cauvery, R. (1992), "Instability in Tamil Nadu groundnut production". *Agricultural Situation in India* , **67**(7): 575-580.
6. Chahal S. S., Singh R. H., Singh S. (2003), "A study into Growth Analysis of production and Acreage Response of Cotton in Punjab." *Agricultural Situation in India*, **60** (1) April: 3-10
7. Degaonkar, A.M., More, D.G. and Kirtiwar, V.L. (1996), "Measurement of Risk in cotton yield in the Marathwada region". *Journal. cotton Research and development*, **10** (1): 51-55.
8. Deka, N. and Sarmah, A.K. (2004), "Growth trends in area, production and productivity of Banana in Assam". *Agricultural Situation in India*, **61** (3) :: 131-132.
9. Gaddi, G.M., Amrutha, C.P. and Patil, S.A. and Dabali, S.D. (1998), "Progress of cotton : A growth rate analysis". *Agricultural Banker*, **2** (4) : 17-25.
10. Goswami, S.N., Choudhury, A.N. and Sarma, B.K. (1995), "Growth trend of oilseeds and pulses in India". *Agricultural Situation in India*, **52**(4) : 191-193.
11. Haffis, S., Reedy, Y.V.R., Lakshmi, P. and Raju, R.K. (1992), "Growth patterns in food grains economy of India". *Agricultural Situation in India*, **66** (12): 905-908.